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CLINICAL IMPACT OF DRUG-DRUG INTERACTIONS ON PATIENT SAFETY AND OUTCOMES IN CLINICAL TRIALS: THE ROLE OF THE HOSPITAL PHARMACIST

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ABSTRACT

INTRODUCTION: Drug-drug interactions (DDIs) are a clinically significant factor that modulates patient safety and therapeutic outcomes in clinical trials. Participants with comorbidities are frequently exposed to multiple concomitant medications, increasing the risk of pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic interactions.

AIM: The aim of this review is to evaluate the clinical impact of DDIs on patient safety and treatment outcomes in clinical trial settings, with emphasis on the role of the hospital pharmacist.

MATERIALS AND METHODS: A structured review of published literature and clinical guidelines was conducted, including sources from the last 6 years and from the following scientific databases: PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science, as well as the European Medicines Agency and the U.S. Food and Drug Administration. The analysis focused on clinically relevant DDIs, their association with adverse events, and their impact on treatment response.

RESULTS: Clinically significant DDIs were most frequently observed in patients with polypharmacy, particularly in oncology and cardiovascular trials. High-risk interactions included CYP3A4 inhibitors and inducers leading to altered drug exposure, QT interval-prolonging drug combinations associated with arrhythmias, and interactions involving anticoagulants with increased bleeding risk. These interactions were linked to higher rates of adverse drug reactions, dose adjustments, and treatment discontinuation. Pharmacist-led medication review and DDI screening were identified as key strategies for early detection and prevention of clinically relevant interactions.

CONCLUSION: Drug-drug interactions pose a significant clinical challenge in the conduct of clinical trials and may compromise both patient safety and treatment outcomes. Active involvement of hospital pharmacists in medication review, DDI screening, and risk management is essential for optimizing patient care and ensuring reliable clinical trial results.

Keywords: *drug-drug interactions, hospital pharmacist, clinical trials, CYP3A4-inhibitors, patient safety*